

To Study the Adoption/utilization of S.B.M.(Swachh Bharat Mission) Facilities by the Respondents

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Abstract

"Sanitation is more important than independence".

Mahatma Gandhi

The present study was conducted in Baghpat district of Uttar Pradesh. The state Uttar Pradesh has 75 districts. Among all the states, Uttar-Pradesh is so much populated in a very large amount which comprised 16.5 percent total population of India in 2011. (Source-Census report, 2011). India covers 17.5 per cent of the world population. The condition of, hygiene and sanitation, facility of drinking water was very gigantic since large decades. The irrelevant behavior in order to address this challenge was responsible for the many risks were faced by respondents. The study revealed that the majority of respondents 79.00% were using their own toilet and out of 79 respondents 40.50% (32) were using toilet in every time and minimum 02.53% respondents, toilet use only children. It was found that 21.00% respondents were not using toilet and out of 21 respondents 23.80% (5) were not use of toilet, they stated toilet construction is not good. Through the study, it was found that the majority of respondents 87.00% disposed of wet and dry garbage with mix and only 11.00% throwing household garbage and dung in constructed pit.

Keywords Sanitation, Construction, Garbage and Respondents.

Introduction

Cleanliness and sanitation were an integral part of Gandhian way of living. His dream was total sanitation for all. He used to emphasize that cleanliness is the most important for physical wellbeing and a healthy environment.

India is the 7th largest country in the world and 2nd most populated nation in the world. As per census report 2011, the population of India comprised 1.21 billion. The literacy rate of country 74.04 per cent, 82.14 per cent for male literacy and 65.46 per cent for female literacy. Suitable reasons behind the rapidly growing India's population are poor financial condition of the people, lack of proper education, and increased level of birth rate etc. Nearly 30 per cent population of India affected by poverty. It was found in the report of United Nation Development Program in 2014 that multidimensional Poverty Index showed 56 per cent people in India had poor status in the section of education, health, sanitation and standards of living indicators. Poor sanitation continues to have a significant impact on the country. The report of united nation revealed that, 55 percent people in India were defecating in the open. Defecation in open causes spreading many diseases through insect moving from one place to another.

The 1981 Census revealed rural sanitation coverage was only around 1 percent. The lack of sanitation had been a leading cause of diarrhea among children (under five year) resulting in stunting among children and also resulted in several preventable child deaths. Sanitation is also a critical aspect for ensuring safety and dignity for women. In 1986 a programme Central Rural Sanitation Programme (CRSP) which solely focused on sanitation was introduced. The first nationwide centrally sponsored programme aimed to provide safe sanitation in rural areas. Since the programme did not address the question of Open Defecation, it did not provide desired results.

According to the census of 2011, 53.1 per cent (63.6 per cent in 2001) of the households in India do not have a toilet, with the percentage being as high as 69.3 per cent (78.1 per cent in 2001) in rural areas and 18.6 per cent (26.3 per cent in 2001) in urban areas. These facts have also been reconfirmed by another report released on 6th March 2012 by the WHO/UNICEF's Joint Monitoring Programme on sanitation for the Millennium Development Goals, which has also indicated that 59 per cent (626 million) Indians still do not have access to toilets and practice open defecation and that majority of them live in rural areas.

Need For Swachh Bharat Mission

Sanitation is the basic need of human beings. Safe sanitation is not a borrowed modern concept from the West rather there is historical evidences in India's ancient civilization (Sindhu Valley) regarding scientific methods used in toilet construction and waste management. But hundreds of years of servility took away the important value of Swachhata from India's social system. Despite the widely accepted fact related to the critical importance of sanitation and personal hygiene, sanitation coverage of India was as low as 39 percent till 2014. Around 55 crore people in rural areas were without a toilet facility before 2014. This was severely affecting the health and dignity of people in rural areas, especially women and children.

In 2012, the Central Government launched Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan (NBA), with an aim to provide 100 percent access to toilets in rural households by 2022. NBA was launched in convergence with Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA). NBA was an update of TSC with renewed strategies and modified guidelines and objectives to accelerate sanitation coverage in the rural areas. An inefficient solid and liquid waste management system create serious negative environmental impacts like infectious diseases, land and water pollution, obstruction of drains and loss of biodiversity. Mane (2014) found in his study that 1000 children die daily in India from diarrhea, which was spreading due to defecating in open, unhygienic Condition, and poor sanitation. Access to poor sanitation is not just unpleasant, it is dangerous, when people have no option but to defecate in the open, they run the risk of catching or spreading an infectious disease like diarrhea, cholera. Women and girls are particularly vulnerable when they do not have access to a private toilet. Beyond health risks, poor sanitation can have several negative impacts. It leaves women and girls open to the dangers of harassment and assault by men and attacks by animals (Geertz et al., 2018), (Saleem, Burdett, & Heaslip, 2019) (Sommer, Ferron, Cavill, & House, 2015). It is India's biggest ever cleanliness drive and 3 million government employees and school and college students of India participated in this event. The core objectives of the Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) are to bring about an improvement in the general quality of life in the rural areas, by promoting cleanliness, hygiene and eliminating open defecation and to accelerate sanitation coverage in rural areas to achieve the vision of Swachh Bharat by 2nd October 2022.

The main objectives of the Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) are-

1. To bring about an improvement in the general quality of life in the rural areas, by promoting cleanliness, hygiene and eliminating open defecation.
2. To accelerate sanitation coverage in rural areas to achieve the vision of Swachh Bharat by 2nd October 2019.
3. To motivate Communities and Panchayati Raj Institutions to adopt sustainable sanitation practices and facilities through awareness creation and health education.
4. To encourage cost effective and appropriate technologies for ecologically safe and sustainable sanitation.
5. To develop where required, Community managed sanitation systems focusing on scientific Solid & Liquid Waste Management systems for overall cleanliness in the rural areas.

Swachh Bharat Mission in Uttar Pradesh

Out of all state of India, the population of Uttar Pradesh comprised 16.5 per cent of India in 2011 in which 22.27 per cent people have been living in urban regions while 77.33 per cent in rural area. Out of 22 million households, 27.6 per cent have water closet toilet, 4.2 per cent have pit toilet, 1.7 per cent have other toilet and 64.4 people have no toilet and they were practicing open defecation which was a major sanitation challenge in Uttar Pradesh.

Aim of study

The objective of this paper is to study the adoption/utilization of S.B.M.(Swachh Bharat Mission) facilities by the respondents.

Review of Literature

WASH Media-South Asia (2012) stated that more than 1 billion people in South Asia do not have access to improved sanitation facilities, while around 700 million practice open defecation. The report further remarks that in 2006, as per the figures given by The World Bank, the consequences of inadequate sanitation cost India approximately \$53.8 billion, which amounts to 6.4% of its GDP.

Amarendra Das, Bibhunandini Das (2015), analysis showed that the chances of stomach problem for households that have access to latrine and bathroom reduce by 6% and 19% respectively in comparison to households without latrine and bathroom. Other sanitation indicators like arrangements for garbage collection and garbage deposit have significant impact on stomach problem. If arrangements are made for collecting garbage and depositing in either bio-gas plant or manure pit than dumping it outside then chances of suffering from stomach problem for those households reduce by 19% and 10% respectively.

Vidhya Venugopal et al. (2016) found that exposure to hot work environments and inadequate sanitation facilities at their workplaces directly contribute to risks such as heat-related stress and genitourinary problems. For example, those women who lacked access to toilets had a six times higher prevalence of kidney damage due to a limited fluid intake so as to reduce the necessity of urination. In addition, 10 per cent of the women reported they suffered economic loss as they had to stay at home on days of their menstrual period.

R Anuradha et al. (2017) revealed that the prevalence of usage of household sanitary latrine and community latrines was 62.5% and 4.3% respectively. The prevalence of open-air defecation among the study participants was 33.1%. Significant association was found between low standard of living and open-air defecation practice.

WHO (2018) estimated that Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM)- Grameen will result in averting more than 300000 deaths (diarrhoea and protein-energy malnutrition) between 2014 and October 2019.

UNICEF (2018) revealed that the Swachh Bharat Mission (Gramin) is highly cost-beneficial from both a financial and an economic perspective. Even households that invest INR 16,000 (US \$248) of their own money in a toilet and hand washing station will see those funds repaid in 2 years from the medical costs saved.

Economic Survey (2018-19) stated 67 years after India's independence, in 2014, around 10 crore rural and about 1 crore urban households in India were without a sanitary toilet; over 56.4 crore, i.e., close to half the population, still practiced open defecation. Through SBM, 99.2 per cent of the rural India has been covered. Since October 2, 2014 over 9.5 crore toilets have been built all over the country and 564,658 villages have been declared ODF.

Utsav Raj et al, (2019) revealed that only 38 of 98 surveyed adolescent girls had access to independent toilet facility, 9 were practicing open defecation, and the remaining 51 were using public toilets. Slum report 2014 Raipur stated that more than 35% of the households living in slums defecated in the open. Public toilet users complained about lack of privacy [29 (56.9%)] while using toilets; 7 (13.7%) and 4 (7.8%), respectively, complained of hygiene and bad smell while using it. About 66% of the public toilet users complained about guys gathering around the toilets, and 25% reported that they were abused while using toilets.

Chittaranjan Subudhi (2019) revealed that the respondents 100% (60) had agreed that, they have the knowledge on SBM. 83.3% (50) of the respondent has recognized the behavioural changes occurred after implementing SBM while 16.7% (10) reported no changes, after implementing on SBM. Regarding the practice of open defecation, (8) 13.4% of the respondents are always practicing, (27) 45% sometimes, (3) 5% rarely, and (22) 36.6% never practice. To the question of discouraging factors of toilet usage, (25) 41.6% of the respondents told, they don't have the habit, (4) 6.7% are not using toilet because of lack of water supply, (2) 3.3% quoted long distance, and (29) 48.3% had no discouraging factors.

Anju bala (2021) revealed that the Poor hygienic and cleanliness are the two major causes of illness. Swachh Bharat Mission will have positive impact on India's health care

sector. According to recent study by WHO. Due to lack of hygienic conditions and lack of cleanliness there is a loss of Rs. 6500 every year to each Indian. In short, there is a loss of Rs. 26000 every year for a family of four people. Swachh Bharat Mission will plug this loss and will help to ease burden on existing health care facilities.

Methodology

There were 75 districts in Uttar Pradesh in which Baghpat district of western Uttar Pradesh was selected for study. Out of 6 blocks of Baghpat district two blocks Baghpat and Baraut were selected purposively. Out of these two blocks 2-2 villages from each block were selected and out of these 2-2 villages, 25-25 beneficiaries of S.B.M. were taken for the study. Hence, all together (25 respondents of 4 villages) 100 respondents were the total number of sample size. As far (11 independent variable like age, sex, caste, education etc.) and (3 dependent variable like knowledge, utilization/adoption, problems) concluded for bring out the outcomes under this study. Collection of data was done by personal structured interview schedule and official website of ministry of drinking water and sanitation and the collected data were examined by suitable statistics methods as per need to bring fruitful implications. Outcomes of this study had been presented in the section of result & discussion in a very sequential manner. Ex post facto research design and multistage sampling was used for the study, and after collection of data it was appropriate classified into tables.

Variables and their measurements

The variables were selected according to objectives of study. The variables were categorized into two parts i.e., independent variables and dependent variables.

Dependent variable

Adoption /utilization of S.B.M. facilities by the respondents

Adoption is a decision to make full use of an innovation. In this context it was to determine the extent to which a person utilized the resource available. This can be attributed agree and disagree to with score of 2 and 1 respectively.

1. Opinion of respondents regarding utilization of toilet facility.

S. No.	Opinion	Yes (2)	No (1)
1	Use in every time		
2	Use in Some time		
3	The weather is unfavorable like Cold, Rainy and Summers etc.		
4	When you are Hurry.		
5	When you feel Illness.		
6	Time of Night.		
7	When the Guest in home.		
8	Toilet use only women		
9	Toilet use only Children.		
10	Toilet use only old person.		

Statistical Analysis of Data

After collection of data, following statistical method were used for the analysis of data-

- a. **Tabulation and classification**
- b. **Frequency and percentage**
- c. **Arithmetic mean**

Tabulation and classification:Total data were classified in different group/categories and there after tabulated.

Frequency and percentage:Frequency was calculated to find out the number of respondents in a particular category. The percentage value was calculated by dividing the frequency of a particular cell by total number of respondents in particular category and multiplying by 100.

$$\text{Percentage} = (\text{Value} / \text{Total value}) \times 100$$

or

$$P (\%) = n \times 100 / N$$

Where,

P= percentage

n = frequency of particular cell

N = total number of respondents in the particular category

Arithmetic mean:

Arithmetic mean is defined as the sum of values of observation divided by the total number of observation. Mean is measure of central tendency of the observed phenomena. Symbolically, it is represented as:

$$\text{Arithmetic mean} = \{ \text{Sum of Observation} \} \div \{ \text{Total numbers of Observations} \}$$

$$\text{Mean } (\bar{x}) = \frac{\sum x}{n}$$

X = Average or Mean

$\sum X$ = Total number of scores obtained by Respondent

N= Total Number of Respondents.

Result and Discussion

To study the adoption /utilization of S.B.M. facilities by the respondents. Are dividing in three parts as follow;

1. Opinion of respondents regarding utilization of toilet.
2. Opinion of respondents regarding causes of not utilization of toilet.
3. Opinion of respondents regarding waste management.

1. Opinion of respondents regarding utilization of toilet

Since the implementation of Swachha Bharat Mission maximum focus was given on construction & utilization of toilet to make India open defecation free.

Table 1. Opinion of respondents regarding utilization of toilet (No. =79)

S. No.	Opinion	Frequency	Percentage
1/1	Use of toilet in every time	32	40.50
1/2	Use of toilet in Some time	9	11.39
1/3	When the weather is unfavorable like Cold, Rainy and Summers etc.	7	08.86
1/4	When you are Hurry.	5	06.32
1/5	When you feel Illness.	3	03.79
1/6	Time of Night.	6	07.59
1/7	When the Guest in home.	3	03.79
1/8	Toilet use only women	8	10.12
1/9	Toilet use only Children.	2	02.53
1/10	Toilet use only old person.	4	05.06
	Total	79	99.95

Mean =79/10=7.9

There were 79 respondents use of toilet out of 100 respondents. The description in detail is given in above table that indicates that the maximum respondents 40.50% were using their own toilet in every time, followed by 11.39% in some time. It is also found that the 10.12% were using the toilet only women, 8.86% respondents were used toilet when weather is unfavourable like cold, rainy, summer etc. and 7.59% were using toilet time of night.

It may be concluded that the maximum respondents were utilizing toilet in every time i.e. 40.50 % and minimum 02.53% respondents, toilet use only children were found. And found overall mean in case of adoption of toilet in their house was 7.9 in out ten point respectively.

2. Opinion of respondents regarding causes of not utilization of toilet

Table:2 Opinion of respondents regarding causes of not utilization of toilet (No. =21)

S. No.	Opinion	Frequency	Percentage
2/1	Toilet Construction is not good.	5	23.80
2/2	There is no gate in the toilet.	2	09.52

2/3	There is no water facility.	1	04.76
2/4	The ceiling is not properly constructed.	1	04.76
2/5	The toilet release smells proper.	2	09.52
2/6	Toilet pit is not constructed well.	3	14.28
2/7	Toilet constructed nearby kitchen	1	04.76
2/8	Toilet construction is incomplete.	1	04.76
2/9	The light facility is not available.	1	04.76
2/10	Toilet mattress fills up quickly.	4	19.04
	Total	21	99.96

Mean=21/10=2.1

Table 5:3:2 clearly shown that the maximum of respondents 23.80% were not use of toilet they stated that the toilet construction is not good, followed by 19.04% stated toilet mattress fill up quickly,14.28% were not utilize toilet because toilet pit is not constructed well, 9.52% were not used toilet because there were no gate in toilet and toilet release smells proper, and 4.76% were not utilize toilet because there were no water facility, light facility and selling is not properly constructed, toilet construction is incomplete.

It may be concluded that the maximum i.e., 23.80% respondents were not utilizing toilet because toilet construction is not good. And found overall mean was not use of toilet in their house,ie.2.1 in out of ten point.

3- Opinion of respondents regarding waste management. It is essential to know the various key points which were included in S.B.M. to improve the cleanliness & hygiene in rural areas. Solid and liquid waste management is one of the key components of this programme.

In present study the special focus was given to waste management practices followed by respondents (rural community) in their day-to-day life.

Table 3 Opinion of respondents regarding waste management.

S. No.	Opinion	Agree	Disagree
3/1	Dispose of wet and dry wastage with mix.	87 (87.00%)	13 (13.00%)
3/2	Use of covered dustbin in your home.	35 (35.00%)	65 (65.00%)
3/3	Throwing household garbage and dung in constructed pit.	11 (11.00%)	89 (89.00%)

3/4	Throwing household garbage and dung on the side of the road.	76 (76.00%)	24 (24.00%)
3/5	Throwing household garbage and dung on the side of ponds.	42 (42.00%)	58 (58.00%)
3/6	Throwing household garbage and dung in corner of field.	74 (74.00%)	26 (26.00%)
3/7	Using soak pit for liquid waste management.	17 (17.00%)	83 (83.00%)
3/8	Use of liquid waste in kitchen garden.	24 (24.00%)	76 (76.00%)
3/9	Open burning of solid waste.	47 (47.00%)	53 (53.00%)
3/10	Throwing wastage in open place.	29 (29.00%)	71 (71.005%)

Table 3. shows that the majority 87.00% were dispose of wet and dry garbage with mix, followed by 76.00% throwing household garbage and dung on the side of road, 74.00% respondents throwing household garbage and dung in corner of field, 47.00% respondents open burning of solid waste, 42.00% respondents throwing household garbage and dung on the side of ponds, 35.00% respondents used covered dustbin in their home, 29.00% respondents throwing wastage in open place, and 24.00% respondents used of liquid waste in kitchen garden, 17.00% respondents using soak pit for liquid waste management, 11.00% respondents throwing household garbage and dung in constructed pit.

Conclusion

It is revealed form the study that 40.50 percent of respondents had access to toilet every time whereas 23.80 percent of respondents had dissent that the construction of toilet is not good. Toilet mattress fills up quickly were noted opinions by the respondents. Regarding dry waste disposal of waste and dry wastage with mix 87 per cent agreed with waste management.

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